

On Hankel determinant inequalities

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Abstract. We derive the Hankel determinant inequalities for inverse starlike and convex functions.

Introduction

Let S denote the class of normalised analytic univalent functions $f(z)$ in the unit disk $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C}, |z| < 1\}$, which have the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$$

We recall the following:

Definition 1.1. Let f be given by (1.1). Then $f \in S^*$ if and only if

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right\} > 0, \quad z \in U.$$

Definition 1.2. Let f be given by (1.1). Then $f \in \mathcal{C}$ if and only if

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} + 1 \right\} > 0, \quad z \in U.$$

The inverse f^{-1} of every function $f \in S$, defined by $f^{-1}(f(z)) = z$, is analytic in $|w| < r(f)$, ($r(f) \geq \frac{1}{4}$) and has Maclaurin's series expansion

$$f^{-1}(w) = w + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} b_n w^n, \quad (|w| < r(f))$$

Early in 1923 Löwner [5] invented the famous parametric method to find sharp bounds on all the coefficients for the inverse functions in S (or S^*). Thus if $f \in S$ (or S^*) is given by (1.4) then

$$|b_n| \leq \frac{1}{n+1} \binom{2n}{n}; \quad (n = 2, 3, \dots)$$

with equality for every n for the inverse of the Koebe function $K(z) = \frac{z}{(1+z)^2}$. Further, if $f \in \mathcal{C}$ then $|b_n| \leq 1$, ($n = 2, 3, \dots, 8$), while $|b_{10}| > 1$ See [5].

In [3], the q th Hankel determinant for $q \geq 1$ and $n \geq 0$ is stated by Noonan and Thomas as

$$H_q(n) = \begin{vmatrix} a_n & a_{n+1} & a_{n+q+1} \\ a_{n+1} & \dots & \cdot \\ \cdot & & \\ a_{n+q-1} & \dots & a_{n+2q-2} \end{vmatrix}.$$

This determinant has been considered by several authors. For example, in [1] the Hankel determinant was considered in case $q = 2$ and $n = 2$,

$$H_2(2) = \begin{vmatrix} a_2 & a_3 \\ a_3 & a_4 \end{vmatrix}.$$

In [1] authors found upper bound for the functional $|a_2 a_4 - a_3^2|$ for functions f belongs to the class S^* and \mathcal{C} . The objective of this paper is to seek upper bound for the functional $|b_2 b_4 - b_3^2|$ for the inverse function f^{-1} given by (1.4) for f belonging to S^* and \mathcal{C} .

Notations and Preliminary Results

Let the function s given by the power series

$$s(z) = 1 + d_1 z + d_2 z^2 + \dots$$

be analytic in a neighborhood of the origin. For a real number l define the function h by

$$h(z) = (s(z))^l = (1 + d_1 z + d_2 z^2 + \dots)^l = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k^{(l)} z^k.$$

Thus $C_k^{(l)}$ denotes the k^{th} coefficient in Maclaurin's series expansion of the l^{th} of the function $s(z)$.

Lemma 2.1([9]). Let the coefficients $C_k^{(l)}$ be defined as in (2.2), then

$$C_{k+1}^{(l)} = \sum_{j=0}^k \left[l - \frac{(l+1)j}{k+1} \right] d_{k+1-j} C_j^l; \quad (k = 0, 1, \dots; C_0^l = 1).$$

Let P be the family of all functions p analytic in U for which $\Re p(z) > 0$ and

$$p(z) = 1 + c_1 z + c_2 z^2 + \dots$$

for $z \in U$.

Lemma 2.2([4]) If $p \in P$ then $|c_k| \leq 2$ for each k .

Lemma 2.3([2]) The power series for p given by (2.4) converges in U to a function in P if and only if the Toeplitz determinants

$$D_n = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & c_1 & c_2 \dots & c_n \\ c_{-1} & 2 & c_1 \dots & c_{n-1} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ c_{-n} & c_{-n+1} & c_{-n+2} \dots & 2 \end{vmatrix}, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

and $c_{-k} = \bar{c}_k$, are all nonnegative. they are strictly positive except for $p(z) = \sum_{k=1}^m \rho_k \rho_0 (e^{it_k z})$, $\rho_k > 0$, t_k real and $t_k \neq t_j$ for $k \neq j$; in this case $D_n > 0$ for $n < m - 1$ and $D_n = 0$ for $n \geq m$.

Main Result

Theorem 3.1. Let f^{-1} be defined in (1.4), if $f \in S^*$. Then

$$|b_2 b_4 - b_3^2| \leq 3$$

.

The result is sharp.

Proof. We know from [8] that

$$b_n = \frac{1}{2\pi i n} \int_{|z|=r} \frac{1}{(f(z))^n} dz.$$

Now for fixed n we write

$$h(z) = \left[\frac{z}{f(z)} \right]^n = \frac{1}{(1 + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^{k-1})^n} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k^{(-n)} z^k.$$

Thus

Now, by using (lemma 2.1) and (3.3) we can directly calculate the following:

$$\left(\frac{z}{f(z)} \right)^2 = \left(1 + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^{k-1} \right)^{-2} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k^{(-2)} z^k.$$

$$\left(\frac{z}{f(z)} \right)^3 = \left(1 + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^{k-1} \right)^{-3} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k^{(-3)} z^k.$$

$$\left(\frac{z}{f(z)} \right)^4 = \left(1 + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^{k-1} \right)^{-4} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C_k^{(-4)} z^k.$$

which yields

$$\begin{aligned} b_2 &= -a_2 \\ b_3 &= -a_3 + 2a_2^2 \\ b_4 &= -a_4 + 5a_2 a_3 - 5a_2^3 \end{aligned}$$

Since $f \in S^*$, it follows from (1.2) that there exists $p \in P$ such that

$$zf'(z) = f(z)p(z)$$

Equating coefficients in (3.8) yields

$$\begin{aligned} a_2 &= c_1 \\ a_3 &= \frac{c_2}{2} + \frac{c_1^2}{2} \\ a_4 &= \frac{c_3}{3} + \frac{c_1 c_2}{2} + \frac{c_1^3}{6} \end{aligned}$$

So, it follows from (3.7) and (3.9) that:

$$\begin{aligned} b_2 &= -c_1 \\ b_3 &= -\frac{c_2}{2} + \frac{3c_1^2}{2} \\ b_4 &= -\frac{c_3}{3} + 2c_1c_2 - \frac{8c_1^3}{3} \end{aligned}$$

From (3.10), we find that

$$|b_2b_4 - b_3^2| = \left| \frac{1}{3}c_1c_3 - \frac{1}{4}c_2^2 + \frac{5}{12}c_1^4 - \frac{1}{2}c_1^2c_2 \right|$$

Using Lemma 2.3 we obtain the upper bound of (3.11). We assume that $c_1 \geq 0$. Rewriting (2.5) for the cases $n = 2$ and $n = 3$, result in

$$D_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & c_1 & c_2 \\ c_1 & 2 & c_1 \\ \bar{c}_2 & c_1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 8 + 2\Re\{c_1^2c_2\} - 2|c_2|^2 - 4c_1^2 \geq 0,$$

which is equivalent to

$$2c_2 = c_1^2 + x(4 - c_1^2)$$

for some x , $|x| \leq 1$.

Further, $D_3 \geq 0$ is equivalent to

$$|(4c_3 - 4c_1c_2 + c_1^3)(4 - c_1^2) + c_1(2c_2 - c_1^2)^2| \leq 2(4 - c_1^2)^2 - 2|2c_2 - c_1^2|^2;$$

and this, with (3.12), provide the relation

$$4c_3 = c_1^3 + 2(4 - c_1^2)c_1x - c_1(4 - c_1^2)x^2 + 2(4 - c_1^2)(1 - |x|^2)z$$

for some z , $|z| \leq 1$.

Suppose that $c_1 = c$ and $0 \leq c \leq 2$. Using (3.12) along with (3.13), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3}c_1c_3 - \frac{1}{4}c_2^2 + \frac{5}{12}c_1^4 - \frac{1}{2}c_1^2c_2 \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{3c^4}{16} + \frac{(4 - c^2)(1 - |x|^2)cz}{6} - \frac{(4 - c^2)(c^2 + 12)x^2}{48} - \frac{5(4 - c^2)c^2x}{24} \right| \end{aligned}$$

Application of the triangle inequality gives

$$\left| \frac{1}{3}c_1c_3 - \frac{1}{4}c_2^2 + \frac{5}{12}c_1^4 - \frac{1}{2}c_1^2c_2 \right| \leq \frac{3c^4}{16} + \frac{c(4 - c^2)}{6} + \frac{(4 - c^2)(c - 2)(c - 6)y^2}{48} + \frac{5(4 - c^2)c^2y}{24}$$

with $y = |x| \leq 1$. Furthermore,

$$F'(y) = \frac{5c^2(4 - c^2)}{24} + \frac{(4 - c^2)(c - 2)(c - 6)y}{24}$$

it can be shown that $F'(y) > 0$ and thus $F(y)$ is increasing function which implies that it attained its maximum at $y = 1$ and $c = 2$, in which case

$$\left| \frac{1}{3}c_1c_3 - \frac{1}{4}c_2^2 + \frac{5}{12}c_1^4 - \frac{1}{2}c_1^2c_2 \right| \leq 3$$

Equality is attained for $K^{-1}(z)$, where $K(z)$ is the Koebe function.

This completes the proof of theorem 3.1. \square

Theorem 3.2. Let f^{-1} be defined in (1.4), if $f \in \mathcal{C}$. Then

$$|b_2b_4 - b_3^2| \leq \frac{1}{8}$$

.

The result is sharp.

Proof. Since $f \in \mathcal{C}$, it follows from (1.3) that there exists $p \in \mathcal{P}$ such that

$$(zf'(z))' = f'(z)p(z)$$

Equating coefficients in (3.15) we get

$$\begin{aligned} a_2 &= \frac{c_1}{2} \\ a_3 &= \frac{c_2}{6} + \frac{c_1^2}{6} \\ a_4 &= \frac{c_3}{12} + \frac{c_1c_2}{8} + \frac{c_1^3}{24} \end{aligned}$$

Now, (3.7) together with (3.16) yield

$$\begin{aligned} b_2 &= \frac{-c_1}{2} \\ b_3 &= \frac{-c_2}{6} + \frac{c_1^2}{3} \\ b_4 &= \frac{-c_3}{12} + \frac{7c_1c_2}{24} - \frac{c_1^3}{4} \end{aligned}$$

So, from (3.17), we have

$$|b_2b_4 - b_3^2| = \frac{1}{432} |18c_1c_3 - 15c_1^2c_2 - 12c_2^2 + 6c_1^4|$$

Now, assume that $c_1 = c$, ($0 \leq c \leq 2$), and again using (3.12) together with (3.13) we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & |18c_1c_3 - 15c_1^2c_2 - 12c_2^2 + 6c_1^4| \\ &= \left| -\frac{9c^2(4-c^2)x}{2} - \frac{3(4-c^2)(c^2+8)x^2}{2} + 9c(4-c^2)(1-|x|^2)z \right| \end{aligned}$$

and application of triangle inequality shows that

$$|18c_1c_3 - 15c_1^2c_2 - 12c_2^2 + 6c_1^4| \leq 9c(4-c^2) + \frac{9c^2(4-c^2)y}{2} + \frac{3(4-c^2)(c-2)(c-4)y^2}{2}$$

with $y = |x| \leq 1$. And

$$F'(y) = \frac{9c^2(4 - c^2)}{2} + 3(4 - c^2)(c - 2)(c - 4)y > 0$$

Thus $F(y)$ is an increasing function that attained its maximum at $y = 1$. The upper bound for (3.19) corresponds to $y = 1$ and $c = 1$, in which case

$$|18c_1c_3 - 15c_1^2c_2 - 12c_2^2 + 6c_1^4| \leq 54.$$

Letting $c_1 = 1$, $c_2 = 2$ and $c_3 = 1$ in (3.18) shows that the result is sharp.

This completes the proof of theorem 3.2.

REFERENCES

1. M. Abramowitz and I. A. Stegun (Eds.), Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables, Dover Publications Inc., New York, 1965.
2. A. A. Attiya, Some applications of Mittag-Leffler function in the unit disk, Filomat 30(7) (2016), 2075-2081. <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL1607075A>
3. D. Bansal and J. K. Prajapat, Certain geometric properties of the Mittag-Leffler functions, Complex Var. Elliptic Equ. 61(3) (2016), 338-350. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17476933.2015.1079628>
4. T. Bulboacă and G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Univalent functions with positive coefficients involving Pascal distribution series, Commun. Korean Math. Soc. 35(3) (2020), 867 – 877. <https://doi.org/10.4134/CKMS.c190413>
5. N. E. Cho, S. Y. Woo and S. Owa, Uniform convexity properties for hypergeometric functions, Fract. Calc. Appl. Anal. 5(3) (2002), 303-313.
6. P. L. Duren, Univalent Functions, Grundlehren der Mathematischen Wissenschaften Series 259, Springer Verlag, New York, 1983. [7] M. El-Deeb, T. Bulboacă and J. Dziok, Pascal distribution series connected with certain subclasses of univalent functions, Kyungpook Math. J. 59 (2019), 301-314. <https://doi.org/10.5666/KMJ.2019.59.2.301>
7. B. A. Frasin, An application of an operator associated with generalized Mittag-Leffler function, Konuralp J. Math. 7(1) (2019), 199-202.
8. B. A. Frasin, T. Al-Hawary and F. Yousef, Some properties of a linear operator involving generalized Mittag-Leffler function, Stud. Univ. Babeş-Bolyai Math. 65(1) (2020), 67 – 75. <https://doi.org/10.24193/subbmath.2020.1.06>
9. B. A. Frasin, T. Al-Hawary and F. Yousef, Necessary and sufficient conditions for hypergeometric functions to be in a subclass of analytic functions, Afr. Mat. 30(1-2) (2019), 223-230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-018-0638-5>
10. H. J. Haubold, A. M. Mathai and R. K. Saxena, Mittag-Leffler functions and their applications, J. Appl. Math. 2011(2011), Article ID 298628. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/298628>
11. V. Kiryakova, Generalized Fractional Calculus and Applications, Pitman Research Notes in Mathematics Series 301, Longman Scientific & Technical, Harlow, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1994.
12. E. Merkes and B. T. Scott, Starlike hypergeometric functions, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. 12 (1961), 885-888.
13. G. M. Mittag-Leffler, Sur la nouvelle fonction $E(x)$, C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris 137(1903), 554 – 558.
14. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Subordination results for spiral-like functions associated with the Srivastava-Attiya operator, Integral Transforms Spec. Funct. 23(2) (2012), 97-103. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10652469.2011.562501>

15. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, D. Răducanu and K. Vijaya, A class of spirallike functions defined by Ruscheweyh-type q -difference operator, *Novi Sad J. Math.* **49**(2)(2019),59 – 71. <https://doi.org/10.30755/NSJOM.08284>
16. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, K. Vijaya and S. Porwal, Some inclusion results of certain subclass of analytic functions associated with Poisson distribution series, *Hacet. J. Math. Stat.* **45**(4) (2016), 1101-1107. <https://doi.org/10.15672/HJMS.20164513110>
17. G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Subclasses of starlike and convex functions involving Poisson distribution series, *Afr. Mat.* **28**(2017), 1357-1366. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-017-0520-x>
18. S. Porwal and M. Kumar, A unified study on starlike and convex functions associated with Poisson distribution series, *Afr. Mat.* **27**(5) (2016), 1021-1027. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13370-016-0398-z>
19. M. S. Robertson, On the theory of univalent functions, *Ann. of Math.* (2) **37**(2) (1936), 374-408.
20. Salah, Jamal, Hameed Ur Rehman, and Iman Al-Buwaiqi. "The Non-Trivial Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function through Taylor Series Expansion and Incomplete Gamma Function." *Mathematics and Statistics* **10.2** (2022): 410-418.
21. Rehman, Hameed Ur, Maslina Darus, and Jamal Salah. "Graphing Examples of Starlike and Convex Functions of order β ." *Appl. Math. Inf. Sci.* **12.3** (2018): 509-515.
22. Salah, Jamal Y., and O. M. A. N. Ibra. "Properties of the Modified Caputo's Derivative Operator for certain analytic functions." *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* **109.3** (2014): 665-671.
23. Jamal Salah and Maslina Darus, On convexity of the general integral operators, *An. Univ. Vest Timis. Ser. Mat. -Inform.* **49**(1) (2011), 117-124.
24. Salah, Jamal. "TWO NEW EQUIVALENT STATEMENTS TO RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS." (2019).
25. H. Silverman, Starlike and convexity properties for hypergeometric functions, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* **172** (1993), 574-581. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jmaa.1993.1044>
26. H. M. Srivastava, G. Murugusundaramoorthy and S. Sivasubramanian, Hypergeometric functions in the parabolic starlike and uniformly convex domains, *Integral Transforms Spec. Funct.* **18** (2007),511 – 520. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10652460701391324>
27. L. Spáček, Contribution à la théorie des fonctions univalentes, *Časopis Pro Pěstování Matematiky* **62**(1932), 12 – 19.
28. Salah, Jamal Y. "A new subclass of univalent functions defined by the means of Jamal operator." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)* Vol **108** (2018): 389-399.
29. Jamal Y. Salah On Riemann Hypothesis and Robin's Inequality. *International Journal of Scientific and Innovative Mathematical Research (IJSIMR)*. Volume (3) **4** (2015) 9-14.
30. Salah, Jamal. "Neighborhood of a certain family of multivalent functions with negative coefficients." *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math* **92.4** (2014): 591-597.
31. Salah, Jamal, and Maslina Darus. "A note on Starlike functions of order α associated with a fractional calculus operator involving Caputo's fractional." *J. Appl. comp Sc. Math* **5.1** (2011): 97-101.
32. J. Salah, Certain subclass of analytic functions associated with fractional calculus operator, *Trans. J. Math. Mech.*, **3** (2011), 35–42. Available from: <http://tjmm.edyropress.ro/journal/11030106.pdf>.
33. Salah, Jamal. "Some Remarks and Propositions on Riemann Hypothesis." *Mathematics and Statistics* **9.2** (2021): 159-165.
34. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "The consequence of the analytic continuity of Zeta function subject to an additional term and a justification of the location of the non-trivial zeros." *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* **9.3** (2020): 1566-1569.

35. A. Swaminathan, Certain sufficient conditions on Gaussian hypergeometric functions, *Journal of Inequalities in Pure and Applied Mathematics* 5(4) (2004), Article ID 83, 10 pages.
36. A. Wiman, Über die nullstellen der funktionen $E_\alpha(x)$, *Acta Math.* 29 (1905), 217-134.
37. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "An Alternative perspective to Riemann Hypothesis." *PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION* 57.9 (2020): 1278-1281.
38. Salah, Jamal Y. "A note on the Hurwitz zeta function." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)* 101.12 (2017): 2677-2683.
39. Jamal Y. Salah. Closed-to-Convex Criterion Associated to the Modified Caputo's fractional Calculus Derivative Operator. *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)*. Vol. 101, No. 1, pp. 55-59, 2017, DOI: 10.17654/MS101010055.
40. Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Riemann Zeta Function, *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, vol. 06, no. 02, pp. 07-16, February 2016, URL: [http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20\(part-3\)/B06230716.pdf](http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20(part-3)/B06230716.pdf)
41. Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Gamma Function, *International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology (IJMSET)*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. 58-64, 2015.
42. Salah, Jamal, and S. Venkatesh. "Inequalities on the Theory of Univalent Functions." *Journal of Mathematics and System Science* 4.7 (2014).
43. T. R. Prabhakar, A single integral equation with a generalized Mittag – Leffler function in the kernel, *Yokohama Math. J.* 19 (1971), 7 – 15.
44. Jamal Salah. Subordination and superordination involving certain fractional operator. *Asian Journal of Fuzzy and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 1, pp. 98-107, 2013. URL: <https://www.ajouronline.com/index.php/AJFAM/article/view/724>
45. Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "Two Conditional proofs of Riemann Hypothesis." *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)* 49.1 (2020): 74-83.
46. Salah, Jamal. "Fekete-Szego problems involving certain integral operator." *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology-IJMTT* 7 (2014).